

An Appraisal of Community Policing Practices: A Case Study of Chandigarh, India

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Abstract

Tackling internal insecurity and preventing crime through increased cooperation within society is considered as the paramount solution to rising security concerns. This can only be achieved through establishing mutual trust through continuous efforts by promoting a culture of dialogue. However this dialogue must start at the community level with community policing initiatives that are mapped and executed with a conscientious and concentrated approach. The present study analyzes and evaluates the strategy and initiatives of the public and community relation practices being carried out by the Chandigarh police. The study finds that these practices have shown remarkable benefits through winning trust and plugging the gaps that exist between the public and the police. However to strengthen the spirit of effective public/police interface issues of corruption, lack of professionalism, low morale and conflict among different strata's of Chandigarh police need to be dealt on an immediate basis.

Keywords: Community Policing, Public Police Interface, Chandigarh, India

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Introduction

Today community policing is the lexicon of the global policing framework. This pragmatic shift was neither easy nor adaptive for both the community and the law and order enforcement agencies, as the society transitioned from electronic to informative governance wherein the need and requirement for community policing became an essential ingredient as the role of the police in the society is both unique and problematic. The community is a group of people with a definite culture which experience changes with variations in the politico-socio-economic scenario which brings the various situational, structural and symbolic aspects of policing into forestay.

In democratic societies where various players viz good governance, civil society, non-government institutions, accountability, need for internal security, role of media, etc have come into the mainstream paving way for more risky, reactionary, protective occupational organization; with such features as its bulwark it becomes essentially important for the society to understand the role and importance of community policing, which not only keeps a check on the usage of coercive powers as its prowess but also delivers itself as an interface between the citizens and the guardians of the society to ensure effective means of governance as community policing is an afterthought of good governance.

A city like Chandigarh which boasts of mushrooming socio-economic developments both by the government and the citizens is also scrapped by myriad problems which portray the role and functioning of this occupational organization as a set of dwindling solidarities resting upon the beliefs of authoritarianism, prejudice, cynicism and suspicion. Through this paper we try to abridge certain facets of policing that were completely different from traditional policing but also try to understand and assess certain aspects of society and police which resist the creation of a strong police-public interface.

Community Policing: A Theoretical Framework

The foundations of the historical perspective of community policing began in England in 1829 with the launching of the *London Metropolitan Police District* by Sir Robert Peel. It was started with the initiative to curb the crime rates in London. Peel, the first Chief of Police, is credited with significant developments in policing, which are still practiced today (Patterson, 1995).

The United States of America, which was under the grip of Civil War in the 1860s duplicated the concept of community police services to control multiracial population and to provide them with community services. However, the American scenario was much broader than its British counterpart. As the America witnessed a change in the political fabric from 1830/40 to 1920/30, wherein the police was known for its corrupt, brutal and physically coercive, also tagged by 'Shoot first, ask questions later' (Fisher-Stewart, 2007). The seeds of community development were laid down during the 'Reformative Era' (1930-1970) of policing when the designated officials were engaged in the development of police-public interface by the implementation of new strategies with the increased use of technology. With the onset of 1960s, the American scenario witnessed the chaos of urban riots which compelled police personnel to return to their roots as they were unable to bridge the gap between the community and police, which led to the 'Community Policing Era' - 1970 (2007).

After its impact on the world, the phenomenon of community policing also entered India, in the 1990s when the country was under the influence of socio-economic development, the state of Maharashtra was hit by riots in 1992-93. These initiatives were undertaken to tackle the increasing crime rates in the country and to build the communication link between the police and the public. Thus, whether it is United States of America, hit by urban riots or India, bogged down by communal riots, both took up the initiative of reforming the police services. This was done through both the implementation of strategic planning and community orientation. In these circumstances one can argue that not only are police services a law enforcement agency but the bulwark of establishment of peace lies in its field of endeavour.

The Concept

The term '*community policing*' applies to innovative implementation of planning, developing and strategizing to reach a consensus for the emancipation of the community by the cumulative endeavours of the police and its citizens. It is a holistic term which cannot confine itself to the connotations of a 100 word definition. It is rather a transition from an experiment to a wave of the future. It is a theory which is applied for the benefit of the people, lest an organizational strategy. Most importantly it is 'What the police do!' This doable feature of the police is reformed while the principle of community policing is applied. Furthermore, to study the various dimensions of community policing, we need to take a look at some of its etymological perceptions.

So much to the dynamic ethos of the society, that the term '*community policing*' has different connotations to different people, but since it is 'the people' that forms the crux of this matter, hence its underlying meaning remains the same, but it may mean different to different people. For example, Trojanowicz and Bucqueroux⁸ define community policing as: Trojanowicz, Robert C., and Bonnie Bucqueroux, eds., *Community Policing: How to Get Started*, 2nd ed., Cincinnati, Ohio: Anderson Publishing Co., 1988.

...a new philosophy of policing based on the concept that police officers and private citizens working together in creative ways can help solve contemporary community problems related to crime, fear of crime, social and physical disorder, and neighborhood decay. The philosophy... requires that police departments develop a new relationship with the law-abiding people in the community, allowing them a greater voice in setting local priorities, and involving them in efforts to improve the overall quality of life in their neighborhoods. It shifts the focus of police work from handling random calls to solving problems.

Central to the philosophy of community policing is the emphasis on effective working partnerships with the community (Peak & Glensor, 1999).

Any definition of community policing, therefore, emphasizes the fact that it is an organizational strategy to transform the way of working for the police. This strategy has however focused upon the working of the daily activities of this organization to foster its relationship with the community by adopting a problem-solving approach by the mobilization of the available resources to ensure the public participation in crime reduction and effective service delivery for public safety. However, the application of the concept is widely based upon two theories, namely,

- a) Normative sponsorship theory—It postulates that more people are of good will, hence will cooperate for the facilitation of consensus (Sower, 1957).
- b) Critical social theory—It postulates 'how' and 'why' people coalesce to correct and overcome their politico-socio-economic hurdles that prevent them from having their needs met. Henceforth, it revolves around three core ideas, namely, empowerment, enlightenment and emancipation (Fayer, 1984).

These theories when applied to a given practical situation alter the organizational functioning of the law and order enforcement agency in a nation, resultant being the improvement in the delivery of an array of services for public safety and community development.

In consensus, from the above discussion, it is indicative that community policing has transitioned from an experimental organizational strategy to a wave of futuristic development which involves the interplay of two ingredients, namely, the community and its law and order enforcement agencies i.e. police. It can also be stated that this service rests upon certain important pillars which can be referred to as the '9Ps'.

- 1) *Philosophy*: It is based on the philosophy that to curb the growth of crime rate, social and physical decay of society the police needs to take up proactive, full-service and participative steps.

- 2) *Personalized*: Community policing can be effective and efficient only when both the community and its concerned police are well acquainted for the attainment of shared goals.
- 3) *Policing*: Apart from all essential functions of traditional policing one prime feature that sets it apart is its proactive problem-solving attribute.
- 4) *Patrols*: To acquaint itself with the community its officers may rely on a local source for their interactions.
- 5) *Permanent*: An experiment can become a wave of future only when there is continuity, persistence and longevity in its elements for effective service delivery
- 6) *Place*: Community policing is an empowering procedure which rests upon the feature of decentralization; thus, the immediate police officials need to be empowered to act judiciously within their jurisdiction.
- 7) *Proactive*: The pivotal function of community policing is equated with the reactive crime responses however with proactive management of problems.
- 8) *Partnership*: It is based upon the mushrooming of a cumulative endeavour of the community and police resting upon mutual support and coordination.
- 9) *Problem-solving*: It shifts the focus from the delivery of traditional to qualitative information, making the work of the police positively prominent.

The common elements which define the dimension and frame the impact of community policing (Cordner, 1998) in the society are the following:

Figure 2. A framework of the Impact of Community Policing

Source: Marie Segrave & Jerry Ratcliffe, "Community Policing: A Descriptive Overview", Australian Institute of Criminology, Australian Government, March 2004.

Thus, the theoretical basis of community policing helps us to understand why its impact has a global appeal. Also the fact that it is a new vision which does not strictly conform to the rejection of traditional policing, but builds its virtues on the existing framework of policing. This puts forth a significant aspect in that the time has come to move forward, faster and with a smarter approach equating the role of both, community and police. This includes the building of its strategies in such a manner that the inbreeding of criminal activities which pose threat to internal security can be reduced significantly with the support and partnership of its essential actors to build this new relationship.

On the basis of the above theoretical framework (see Figure 2) nations around the world have implied certain practices in lieu of community policing, some of which (both international and national practices) have harnessed stupendous results, a few are enlisted below in Table 1.

Table 1. Practices in Community Policing

International Practices	Community Policing in India
The Strathclyde Police in U.K. in 1994 set up a special unit to begin the process of 'professionalization' of the forces media relations, with the head being a Superintendent of Police aided by a senior media relations officer with a staff of eight media relation officers, under it.	Chief of Police, Punjab launched 'Operation Night Domination' to instill confidence in the minds of the people during the dark days of terrorism in the State, which was roped in with the involvement of electronic media (100 journalists)
New York Police Commissioner, William Barton was sworn in as the Los Angeles Department in Oct, 2002; he faced a wide variety of both in the department and the community, thence, he launched systems to create an organization wherein the activities would be shared daily with the media.	The Kerala State, India runs a community policing project, JanamaithriSuraksha. The project centres on a beat officer who is in daily contact with the people in a locality, typically with around 1,000 houses. crime reduction up to 50 per cent was achieved in the police station areas of Irinjalakuda, Perinthalmanna, Kochi.
In Holland, the National Crime Intelligence Service is responsible for the production of weekly television crime watch programme, "OpsporingVerzocht".	Amidst the backdrop of Maoism, Odisha has the "Ama Police Community" policing system, in which the project involves a three tier system-beat patrolling, formation of a committee comprising of local people (AmaSamiti) and district advisory committee consisting of senior police officers to review its progress. An estimated 648,793 families in all 34 Ama Police stations of the state have been covered under community policing system.
Baltimore County, United States, has a telephone number through which the citizens get can the crime statistics for their area. The Scottsdale Police in United States runs a city cable programme, a quarterly magazine and a website	To mobilize public participation and police functioning in Himachal Pradesh, the State Government launched the VishwasYojna in November 2000, initially it was introduced in 22 out of 83 police stations of the State, under this scheme a police station is divided into sectors depending upon the wards of Panchayat, wherein, all household members in a sector constitute People's Policing Committee, with a group of 6 respectable persons of the society from that sector, one homeguard, one chowkidaar and a police constable as the Secretary.
Source: ChabraManoj (2013), "Police Reforms: More talk than action", The Tribune, Chandigarh ChoudharyRohit (2013), "Police must brush up its PR skills", The Tribune, Chandigarh.	Source: MukerjeeDoel (2002), "Community Policing Initiatives in India", available at http://www.humanrightsinitiative.org/new/community_policing_experiments_in_india_1.pdf

Furthermore, the police can partner with social, health, education, recreational, etc agencies of the society to amend the withering of the police public relations. This can be coupled with a number of initiatives such as creating a distinct unit with media heads, present its achievements to the society in a recreational manner, shed away its masculine image, build strong partnerships with NGOs/citizens, to build partnerships with both local and national media. However, as there are various initiatives undertaken it is not known if they are successful or a mere waste resources.

Rationale of Public-Police Interface:

The need for the idea of a community police policy has a universal appeal as it is an effective tool for bridging the gap between the police and the community. In spite of this reformative approach the people consider the police as a masculine, skeptical and a force to fear. Thus the requirement for community policing through effective public relations and planning its policing in the field of both police and community benefits is the linchpin of community policing.

Advocates for community policing have highlighted many reasons why community policing is beneficial to society. These arguments were broken down into three areas by Segrave and Ratcliffe (2004), namely,

- 1) Community-specific benefits
- 2) Police-specific benefits
- 3) Shared benefits

Therefore public relations have become the controlling factor in all walks of policing. This is a double-edged sword as on one hand there are innumerable stories of police exhibiting brutality, impunity, insensitivity, masculinity and abuse of power on a daily basis. On the other, there are various examples where they are unable to protect themselves from powerful groups of society, which target the police personnel. Therefore, the society also needs to take an initiative by empowering its resource mobilization so that it can embed its resources in both social and physical environments. This action will mushroom the positive outlook of the people by removing the fear of the taskforce. Apart from several societal aspects, there are certain frontiers of the organization which require polishing. As an agency dealing with coercive measures they need to be motivated with peer benefits focusing upon the positivity of their work which can be achieved by gaining a legitimate community perception of policing.

Furthermore, according to United Nations standards, there should be 270-280 police personnel for every one hundred thousand citizens. In India, it ranges between 150-200 personnel per one hundred thousand and in Bangalore there is one policeman for every 2,000 people. This figure is alarmingly low. The problem lies in the fact that the police are out of resources and hence a need for a programme such as community policing becomes imperative (The Indian Express News Service, Bangalore, 2013). To curb this problem there is the need of creating a balance between the police and the citizens which will lower down the rate of citizen-police conflicts facilitating an effective flow of information between the two leading to a reduction crime rate. As after all whether it is the demand for community policing of a reformative approach of police in the ambit of good governance, it is to establish capacity building of the efficient resources in the society and external management of environment which needs to be insulated against unlawful interference (Chabra, 2013).

Community vs Traditional police relations:

There is need to understand the difference between traditional policing relations and community policing of today's time. Traditional policing is based upon the following core values:

- 1) *Solidarity* – emphasis on shared responsibility and loyalty to other police officers above all others;
- 2) *Authoritarianism* – belief in, and willingness to exercise, power over others, believed to be either a function of the job or personality type;
- 3) *Suspicion* – mistrust of people gained from limited and often negative contact with public; mistrust of people gained from limited and often negative contact with public; a protective response to the uncertainty of the environment and
- 4) *Conservative* – political and social outlook either caused by the moralistic and negative nature of police work or those who are attracted to police work;
- 5) *Prejudicial* – tendency to prejudge others based on values, behaviour and work experience – stereotyping gets the job done but can lead to racism sexism, etc.;
- 6) *Cynicism* – tendency to regard all non police as potential unreliable, unsympathetic and critical of police.
- 7) *Blue collar* – describes the class background and values of most police officers as blue collar or working class, suggests that police cultural values reflect many of the general values and attitudes of working class males. (Murphy, McKenna, "Rethinking Police Governance, Culture and Management", Task Force on Governance and Cultural Change in the RCMP, Public Safety Canada, March 2007, pp 7)

Community policing is based upon the following core values:

- 1) *Goal-Oriented*- To solve problems of crime, disorder and fear in partnership Goal with the affected community - improved relations with members of the public is a welcome byproduct
- 2) *Involvement*- Community policing requires everyone in the department, civilian employees, and line and staff functionaries, to explore how they implement the principles of community policing through their actions on the job.
- 3) *Grassroot Approach* -Through their local Community Police Forum, average citizens can identify problems that deserve police attention and, in this way, assist in setting the policing agenda for a specific area.
- 4) *Trust based relationship* -Through their local Community Police Forum, average citizens can identify problems that deserve police attention and, in this way, assist in setting the policing agenda for a specific area.
- 5) *Bottoms-up Approach* -Influence is from "the bottom up" - citizens help determine priorities and influence police policy. Community policing calls for meaningful organizational change and restructuring.
- 6) *Qualitative Policing* -Success is determined by qualitative measures such as citizen involvement, improvements in the quality of life, and reductions in fear, crime and disorder (Manual on Community Policing Policy, Framework and Guidelines, South African Police Service).

The above core values of community policing show the practices that depict policing at local level as an important tool of police governance in making a crime free society. It is in this backdrop; the present study analyses and evaluates the practices being carried out by Chandigarh Police.

Research Methodology

The present study analyses the various facets of the initiatives of public relation practices carried out by Chandigarh Police. To accomplish the objectives, both primary and secondary sources of information have been used. The secondary data collected from office records comprised of brochures, live programme schedule, media reports and research articles on police. The primary data was collected from the branch of road safety cell of the Chandigarh Police. To ascertain the level of awareness of citizens, 100 citizens' were selected on simple random sampling method. Further to assess the perception of citizens about community policing practices, focussed group discussions were carried out. To corroborate the results unstructured interviews were also carried out. To provide further background and response to concerns interviews were conducted with select police officials at community relation unit and traffic cell unit.

The study has been divided into three sections. The first section provides discussion on Internal Security and governance. The findings of the study are examined in the 'Survey Findings' section. Finally, the paper provides policy prescriptions and suggestions for yielding fruitful results.

Case Background

The city of Chandigarh is one the most planned and clean cities of India (popularly known as 'City Beautiful') with a population of around 900,000. Chandigarh is one the fastest growing cities in India. Chandigarh became a union territory in 1966 and is the joint capital of two states; Punjab and Haryana. The jurisdiction of the Chandigarh Administration is around 114 square kilometers which also includes approximately 25 villages.

The Chandigarh Police (CP) have been playing a key role in keeping the 'City Beautiful' a role model city dreamt by its planner Le-Corbusier. The CP personnel at the higher level are placed from the Union Territories Cadre of Indian Police Service (IPS) as it is a Union Territory (UT). In addition, the IPS officers from Punjab and Haryana join the CP on a deputation basis. Rest of the CP officials such as Inspectors, Sub-Inspectors and Constables belong to Chandigarh UT.

The CP is directly under the Home Secretary of the Union Territory Chandigarh. The Inspector General of Police (IGP) is the head of the Police Department. He is assisted by Deputy Inspector General of Police (DIG). And the officers are further assisted by Senior Superintendent of Police UT Chandigarh, SSP Operations and Training, Superintendent of Police Traffic Police, SP City, Deputy Superintendent of Police, Inspectors, Sub-Inspectors, Head Constables and Constables respectively. For operational purposes, the CP is divided into three Divisions: Central Police Division(3 PS), East Police Division(4PS) and South Police Division.(4PS).The CP has undertaken community policing initiatives from time to time. It has established a cell named Community Relations Unit (CRU) for this purpose of community policing. Some of the community policing initiatives of the CP are studied and analyzed as below.

Survey Findings

Monitoring Verification of Servants/Tenants/Migrants

With the growing opportunities in the city the number of migrants in the form of skilled and unskilled labor is increasing day by day, thereby, to keep a track of all the migrants to maintain security and safety of the city, the beat officials verify and maintain a record of their whereabouts in the concerned Police Station. In case of the suspicion of a crime the file is forwarded to the SSP. For verification a performa is to be filled in by the tenant/ servant/migrant which also includes their permanent address, family details, caste, gender, languages they speak, proof of identification, etc. with their latest photograph attached.

Interaction Programme with Residents:

Chandigarh is divided into various sectors and each sector is divided into four parts, namely, A, B, C, and D with two beats for each sector. The beat officials visit every house to enquire about possible problems and complaints. Beat officials check out the complaints of aggrieved parties which they make through a channel called Public Window (A mechanism specially created to lodge complaint)and try to solve them bycounseling the parties involved. The CP believes that citizen safety is their responsibility, especially, that of the senior citizens. Thus they provide them with security tips such as to lock their home even while going out for short time, to occupy the house almost all the time, to not to leave any kind of note for service people or family members on the door, to ask for credentials from any sales-person who request to enter into your house, to not to trust strangers and open door for unidentified person, to not to let servants have access to the safe and other storage places, etc.

Door-to-Door Visit by Youngsters

Table 2. Community Contact through Youth

S.No	Institution	Sectors	Houses Visited	Person Contacted
1.	MCM- 36	34, 35, 36	1,429	1,213
2.	PGGCG- 11	11,15	1800	1,462
3.	GGSC- 26	27, 28, 30	218	188
4.	Rotary Club	15,16,18,19,21	492	441

Source: Unpublished MPhil Thesis of KaveriTondon "Public Police Interface : A Case Study of Chandigarh"

According to Table 2, the CP joined hands to carry out routine exercise with the youngsters of city colleges and welfare club to spread the 'caution word' door-to-door. In this initiative the CP with youngsters distributed pamphlets to citizens to make them aware about personal safety and security. These pamphlets include symptoms of drug addiction, home safety tips, prevention of theft, safety and security tips, safety of senior citizens and how the Community Relations Officers and Community Liaison Groups work.

Gully Cricket League:

The CP with the collaboration of local media organized a cricket tournament. The tournament was initiated to build community connection through the spirit of a cricket game. The idea behind this

tournament is to make the idle youth play and channel their energies into sport. The intent of Gully Cricket has resulted in a great method to open the way to youth connectivity for engaging them actively in crime prevention. Five hundred twenty eight teams participated in the tournament, a total of 9,469 participants were divided up into 528 teams of boys, 24 teams of girls and 5 teams of physically challenged youngsters. The 12 teams that reached the Super League were encouraged to become an agent for the social campaigns being run on the side lines of the matches and the initiative got a place in Limca's book of record for maximum number of teams participating in a single largest tournament ever (see <http://www.limcabookofrecords.in/recorddetails.aspx?recid=614>).

Regular meetings with the Residents through Associations and Public Meetings

To elicit participation and cooperation from the residents of the city the CP organizes regular meetings with the Resident and Market Welfare Associations and other public meetings (see Table 3). Here participants are requested to voice the problems faced by the residents both at the domestic and commercial levels. Through these meetings a police-public interface is established, wherein, these organizations help in identification, dissemination and verification of criminal activities.

Table 3. Sample of the Number of Public Meetings held in Various Sectors

Source: Compiled from Documents of Community Relation Unit, Chandigarh.

Statistics show that 723 meetings have been held in past through the police stations with 25449 in attendance, similarly in 2013 altogether in 68 meetings held by 11 police stations 2576 citizens attended. In the special scheme called 'know your scheme' 5 meetings took place till (30th November 2013) and 564 cases were disposed. This data is indicative of the strong foothold of the concept of community policing in the city. It further illustrates the mushrooming of the new vision of community emancipation through the enlightenment is a vital organ as the CP foster the empowerment of the vicinity.

Organizing Police Station Visitor's Week

To establish the efficacy of good governance community policing is an integral tool, not only in a state of crisis of governance but also to ensure active citizen participation. Therefore it is necessary that the citizens are acquainted with the working of the law and order enforcement agency in their vicinity. This is established in Chandigarh by various means, one such being the Police Station Visitor's Week. The citizens have an opportunity to assess the services provided by the police, gain insight into functioning of a police station and also to become better acquainted with the police establishment. For the police, evaluation of their services is an input to further improve their services. This initiative was first undertaken by the Altus Global Alliance Worldwide in 2006. There are 20 indicators categorized into five sub-categories, namely,

- 1) Community Orientation
- 2) Physical Conditions
- 3) Equal Treatment of the Public
- 4) Transparency and Accountability
- 5) Detention Conditions

Organizing Traffic Road Safety Week

On the first Monday of every year Road Safety Week is organized for better traffic management and safer roads. It is an initiative in which the government agencies and social organization collectively come forward to mobilize their resources and educate the young generation regarding the pros and cons of traffic management. Also, there are various other recreational activities undertaken by the Education Branch with the government, corporate and public partnerships, e.g. Blood Donation Camp, various competitions, educating exhibitions, transmissions of messages through media and cultural activities

The education branch of Chandigarh Traffic Police also organizes other annual activities to educate the masses, namely, Festival of Gardens; Consumer Forum Fair; Chandigarh Carnival; Republic Day and Independence Day Parade.

Road Safety Education Programmes for Children:

To inculcate the guidelines of traffic safety focusing on internalization of road rules and road discipline the administration following the principle of 'Catch Them Young' initiates several tasks of traffic guidelines to school children in collaboration with the Education Department, which include:

- a) Scheduled visits of school children: The Road Safety Cell is visited on each working day by a batch of 70-80 school children for a structured 3 hour session on road safety from 9AM to noon, comprising of activities such as round of the exhibition hall, screening of road safety movies, practical training, distribution of printed literature, etc.
- b) Unscheduled visits of school children: The Road Safety Cell also allows impromptu visits by school children from 11.30 AM to 1.30 PM. Training inputs that have been detailed above are provided to the children in a relatively compressed format
- c) Visits of school children from other cities: Apart from the schools of U.T. Chandigarh, the Road Safety Cell/Chandigarh Traffic Park (CTP) is also visited by children of various schools from the neighbouring States of Punjab, Haryana and Himachal Pradesh.
- d) Spontaneous visits by children and their parents: The Road Safety Cell/Chandigarh Traffic Park is visited daily by numerous children accompanied by their parents; printed literature is distributed to the visitors.
- e) Outdoor visits by trainers: The Education Department also organizes exhibitions and lectures on road safety for the children in their school premises

Initiatives for Senior Citizens

To ensure the participation of all walks of life, the Chandigarh Police organizes various activities for senior citizens. Where they are told about the various guidelines for safety and security, traffic management and addressal of their problems. This is in collaboration with the Chandigarh Senior Citizen's Association.

Traffic Marshall Scheme

In the wake of improvement of the public-police interface, the CP introduced the concept of Traffic Marshall. Either senior citizens or retired individuals (having knowledge of public dealings) can enroll for community participation with the traffic police to maintain the traffic management in the city. The traffic marshal is provided with the requisite training and after his appointment. Traffic marshal accompanies the officials during their duty hours to resolve any public grievance during the special drive for apprehending violator's. This initiative has widened the horizons of public-police interface.

Problems Faced by Community Policing Initiatives in Chandigarh:

Although community policing practices has shown benefits, there are certain facets which act as hurdle in diligent community policing. Progressive and retrogressive development work simultaneously; thus, the following can be deduced from the citizens as certain negating factors of community policing

On basis of interaction with one hundred citizens many lamented that they are not even aware of certain practices of the community policing initiatives. However, they are still of the view that police have partially succeeded in winning trust among residents. Along with this they reported that lack of awareness is responsible for poor participation. The responses are summed up in following major heads:

- a) Masculine, insensitive and invasive image of the police reinforces the prejudiced mindset of the society.
- b) Lack of professional PR skills leads to identification of endeavours as a mere waste resources.
- c) Poor motivation, high spool of corruption due to centralization and corrupt nexus of politico-bureau edifice
- d) Monotonous policing techniques require timely and active research to facilitate principle and practical administration.
- e) Citizens and media reports highlighted that there are several instances where cops were found guilty of misbehaving, impolite and remained drunk while at job. Several cops are booked for immoral acts like sexual harassment, misusing power and position (e.g. five field cops were recently booked on raping a minor, *The Chandigarh Tribune*, 25 December 2013), which in turn leads to attrition in faith about the spirit of community policing.
- f) According to UN standards- 270-280 personnel/one hundred thousand citizens, whereas in India it ranges from 150-200; this is an alarming situation.

Conclusion

Every society is encountered by a set of myriad problems, which are distinct to a particular community or culture or a group of people enriching their self-sufficiency which defines the term 'community' in community policing. The latest buzz word creating a pragmatic shift in the ethos of the society, though as a concept it may trace its origin to the early 18th Century but the dynamics of the society make it an imperative principle to be followed by the governments, irrespective of their political, social, historical, cultural, economic milieu.

On the contrary, if a group of people are asked as to define the concept of community policing they would come up with distinct answers as it is not possible for anybody, both the preachers and the practitioners of the discipline to define it meticulously; as so much to the complexities of the society and its ingredients that there exists a wide gap between its resultant activities and their realistic accomplishments. With such negating dynamics only one aspect of community policing comes for rescue i.e. good governance, as while the implementation of various strategies of community policing we are focusing upon the establishment of good governance in the society because good governance is a holistic term which steers clear the negation of administration and society, collectively.

As there are many societal problems which have no solution in the edifice of a strong organization such as the Police, rather can find solace only under the creation of an interface between the police and the citizens. Furthermore, they can be addressed only through the interplay of the actors of good governance viz., the----

- Engaging of the stakeholders of the society to increase accountability
- To build capacity building of its resources whilst to ensure their diligent performance.
- Which ensure democratization of its core values for effective decision-making process?
- This can be delivered only when an organization is aware of its purpose and its outcome.

The above discussion makes it evident that the most important ingredient in the process of good governance is the 'community' so whether it is international or national scenario, community policing can be achieved only when it is perceived as a mission. To define a mission is difficult as it has its set of statements, values, beliefs and strategies (Gayle Fisher-Stewart, 2007, pp25).

Therefore, through this paper we have tried to make an attempt to project community policing not only the need of the hour rather the futuristic bulwark of the society, which is to be perceived as a mission

taken with a clear, concise and precise understanding amongst its stakeholders (police and the public) to ensure public safety and community development as its primary purpose and for it needs to catalyze the various actors of good governance.

References:

- Annan, A. Kofi (2005). *A More Secured World: Our Shared Responsibility*. United Nations, New York.
- Arora, Sogani (2011). *Governance in India: Paradigms and Practices*. 2nd Edition, Aalekh Publishers, Jaipur-302001, p 153-163; 27-26.
- Chabra, Manoj (2013). Police Reforms: More talk than action. *The Tribune*, Chandigarh.
- Chandigarh City Government (2013). "What is community policing?" available <http://www.neighborhoodplanning.org/pdf/Community%20Policing.pdf>
- Choudhury, Jayanto N. (2003). Policing India in 2025: Challenges and Issues Ahead. *The Indian Police Journal*, L (1), p. 39, 43, 44.
- Choudhary, Rohit (2013). Police must brush up its PR skills. *The Tribune*, Chandigarh.
- Cordner, Gary and Biebel, Elizabeth. (2003). *Research for Practice: Problem-Oriented Policing in Practice*. National Criminal Justice Reference Service, Document No. 200518, June 2003.
- DovalAjit (2011). Internal Security- Need for Course Correction. Available at <http://www.vifindia.org/article/2011/february/3/Internal-Security%E2%80%93Need-for-Course-Correction>.
- Fisher-Stewart, Gayle (2007). *Community Policing Explained: A Guide for Local Governments*. U.S Department of Justice, Office of Community Oriented Policing Services.
- Goswami, Namrata (2013). *India's Internal Security Situation: Present Realities and Future Pathways*. Institute for Defence Studies and Analysis, New Delhi.
- Kumar, Vinay (2008). Ground Level Policing Suffers from Lack of Motivation. *The Hindu*, Friday, August 1.
- Lalli, Singh (2013). Police needs to drop masculine image. *The Tribune*, Chandigarh.
- Mehta, Akshat (2009). "Internal (In) Security in India Challenges and Response. *The Indian Police Journal*, LVI(4), pp.26-36.
- Mishra, O.P. (2006). Policing in 21st Century: Areas for Concern. *The Indian Police Journal*, LIII (1), pp. 10-11.
- Mohapatra, Debrata (2013). Community Policing to Counter Maoist Menace. *The Times of India*, Bhubaneswar.
- Moily, Verappa (2008). *Second Administrative Reforms Commission: Citizen Centric Administration*. Government of India.
- MukerjeeDoel (2002). Community Policing Initiatives in India. available at http://www.humanrightsinitiative.org/new/community_policing_experiments_in_india_1.pdf
- Nirmal, Anjali (1992). *Role and Functioning of Central Police Organisations*, Uppal Publishing House, New Delhi.
- Patterson, Jeffrey (1995). Community Policing: Learning the Lessons of History. *FBI Law Enforcement Bulletin*, November; www.lectlaw.com/files/cjs07.htm
- Ranjan and Pratap (2011). *State of Internal Security and Home Affairs*. Golden Peacock Publication.
- Segrave, M. and Ratcliffe, J. (2004). *Community Policing: A Descriptive Overview*, Canberra, Australian Institute of Criminology, March 2004.
- Sevak Ram, (2011). India's Security Challenges: A Future Perspective. IIMBanalore, available at <http://www.vifindia.org/article/2011/february/3/Internal-Security%E2%80%93Need-for-Course-Correction>

Case Study

Sharma, D. & Marwah, J. (2013). An Appraisal of Community Policing Practices: A Case Study of Chandigarh, India, *JOAAG*, Vol. 8, No. 1

Singh, Manmohan (2005). Prime Minister's speech at the Conference of Chief Ministers on Internal Security and Law & Order, April 15, available at the Official Website of the Prime Minister of India, <http://pmindia.nic.in/lpeech.asp?id=105>, last accessed on 13th October 2008

Trojanowicz, Robert C., and Bonnie Bucqueroux, eds. (1988). *Community Policing: How to Get Started*. 2nded., Cincinnati, Ohio: Anderson Publishing Co.